

**Should Translink
Expand The Public Transit Network in Vancouver CMA:
An analysis on possibility for public transit system restructure and expansion**

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Introduction

The influx of population into Metro Vancouver poses significant challenges to the existing transportation infrastructures. Road transport's Green house Gas (GHG) emission contributes 45.1% of the 8 billion ton CO₂, therefore reducing GHG emission by optimizing current public transit system in daily travels is key to reduce overall emissions. When comparing to driving a personal vehicle, alternative transport methods have not been efficient, translating into an increased demand in travel while resulting in more greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [3]. Hence, road congestion will only become more of a frequent phenomenon, and negative environmental impacts will also increase as roads reach their capacity much more often. For municipalities in Metro Vancouver to reach their environmental goals of 45% reduction in GHG emission from 2010 levels by 2030, the need for alternative transportation options should be considered [1]. While micromobility transport options such as bicycles and e-scooters are practical and efficient in short distance travel, the demand of mid to long distance travel can only be fulfilled by public transit or private road vehicles (cars). As public transportation methods such as buses and rails have lower maximum GHG emission per passenger Kilometre at 25-92gCO₂-eq/pkm compared to 177gCO₂-eq/pkm for small and medium cars[2]. Therefore, the public transit system undoubtedly plays an important role in the city's transition to sustainable forms of transportation and sustainable future. Furthermore, the demand for intercity travel will also increase considering that population growth is inevitable. Not only does this pose challenges to the current transit system design, additional public transit coverage will also be needed and must be carefully evaluated and analyzed. Translink can consider increasing ridership in subregions outside the City

of Vancouver, finding an alternative funding model, and further expand the current system with transit oriented development to meet future demands.

About Vancouver Census Metropolitan Area

Since public transit system aims to move populations across the region at a daily basis, as such, population information at different sub-regions is crucial when understanding possible areas of demand and investigate flaw in the current system. The Vancouver census metropolitan area (CMA) has a population of 2,642,825 and the average population density of Vancouver CMA is at 918.0 person/sq.km. Vancouver CMA includes municipalities such as the City of Vancouver, Richmond, Delta, White Rock, Surrey, North Vancouver, West Vancouver, Langley, and Burnaby. The three highest population and population density sub-regions are Vancouver, Surrey, and Burnaby.

Table 1: Population and Population density by selected sub-regions (2021)

	Population	Population Density (person/km ²)
Vancouver(CY)	622,248	5,749.9
Surrey(CY)	568,322	1,797.9
Burnaby(CY)	249,125	2,750.7
Richmond (CY)	209,937	1,629.0

Data gather from 2021 census of population released by statistics Canada
 Source: [4]

Vancouver CMA is separated by the Fraser River with only road connections to suburban areas utilizing bridges such as Knight Street Bridge, Oak Street Bridge, Granville Bridge, Lion Gates Bridge, and many more. In addition, SkyTrains have isolated river crossing tracks that connect major cities such as the City of Vancouver, Surrey, and Richmond.

Congestions In Vancouver CMA

Over the decades, Greater Vancouver has become more and more of a hub attracting new immigrants as well as citizens from other provinces to migrate over. As the population continues to increase, the need for cross regional travel will also increase. Due to geographic constraints, it is estimated that there will be over 15 million minutes in overall congestion delay per day [5]. Numbers are expected to increase 40% from September 2017's findings by 2030 [5]. Congestion related economic losses are also estimated to be between 500 million and 1.5 billion, as seen from 2015's data [6]. As seen in Figure 1, congestion mostly takes place at bridge crossings, highways near bridges and eastern regions. Moreover, Translink estimates that congestion related expenses were \$80 million in 2021, and operation budgets have increased between 2–7 million dollars for road-based transit service alone. Indeed, reducing the effects caused by congestion is key to eradicating unnecessary expenses and GHGs[7]. As such, expansion in public transit system can offer addition travel options to reduce congestions and improve service quality.

Figure 1: Estimated travel time delays in 2030 at AM peak period
Source: [5]

Coverage

As of 2019, Translink operates 245 bus routes, three sky train lines accompanied by 53 stations and 79 km of track, one sea bus route, and a West Coast Express with 69 km of tracks [8]. Translink also covers 2,660 lane km and several bridges along with related bike lane infrastructures [8].

While Translink's network spans across Metro Vancouver, the frequent transit network (FTN) does not have sufficient coverage in municipalities other than Vancouver and Burnaby. FTN demonstrates a more comprehensive design of network coverage that has a reasonable 15-minute waiting time [10]. In Figure 2, it is obvious that the City of Vancouver has the most FTN coverage where sub-regions such as Burnaby, Surrey, Langley, and Richmond have only a few FTN available because they possess moderate levels of population density. In addition, current FTN also lacks west to east connections that should connect municipalities such as Richmond, Surrey, and Langley without commuting on less frequent bus routes. Not only does this affect travel time and unnecessary waiting/lead time for transit users, long service frequency also reduces ridership, which drives people to seek alternative transport such as cars which would increase road congestion [11].

T Frequent Transit Network in Metro Vancouver

Figure 2: Frequent Transit Network In Vancouver CMA operated by translink
 Source: [9]

Figure 3: population density heatmap of Vancouver CMA
Generated with data from Canada census 2021
 Source: [4]

“New evidence on walking distances to transit stops” from McGill university also suggests that the optimal service area is 529 m for bus stops and 1259 m for rail based transit stations [12]. Translink’s recommended catchment radius for buses are 400 m and 800 m for future bus rapid transits or SkyTrains [13]. This suggests an

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underestimation of catchment radius from Translink. Routes and stops are designed based on the population within catchment areas, expected service area coverage, stop accessibility, optimization of cost and time for efficiency, and other factors [13][14][15][16]. As a result, underestimation of the radius may give rise to issues such as unexpected demand and accessibility when planning new or adjusting existing bus routes [15].

Ridership

Daily transit ridership in Translink's system is estimated to be 850,000 boardings/day [17]. In the fall of 2021, a total of 2.2 million unique riders were recorded [17]. With a total population in Vancouver CMA roughly equal 2.5 million in 2016, daily boarding represents a third of the total population and more than 85% of the population have utilized Translink's service. There is no doubt that Metro Vancouver relies heavily on Translink to move the population every day.

Furthermore, it is found that road-based transit contributes to 63% of the overall ridership pre-pandemic, and 75% of travel in Metro Vancouver [7]. This suggests that buses play an important role in moving the population amongst inter-regional travel and Translink should further focus on improving FTN coverage and service qualities as suburban areas will only continue to expand.

Average ridership for road-based transit is 530,000 boarding/weekday in the fall of 2021 [7]. From figure 5, Rail based transit contributes 35% of overall ridership, while Expo

and Millennium Lines 25% and Canada Line 10%. This shows that rail based transit is extremely effective at moving the population, given only 79 km of track constructed across Vancouver CMA [8]. When looking at ridership by region, figure 4 shows that Vancouver/UBC area contributes the most ridership at 47%, followed by the Southeast Sector and Burnaby/New Westminster at 17%. The data aligns with the FTN coverage in various municipalities, but it also supports low ridership outside Vancouver. Meanwhile, Surrey contains a large population with the second-highest population density, yet only represents 17% of the overall ridership. This suggests that increasing FTN coverage in these areas should result in an increase in ridership, considering the high density of the region.

Note: Includes bus and SeaBus boardings and Expo-Millennium Line, Canada Line, and West Coast Express station entries. HandyDART boardings are not included as the HandyDART service has different sub-regional boundaries.

Figure 4: Share of Ridership by sub-region (Fall 2022)
Source: [18]

Figure 5: Distribution of Total System-Wide Boarding by Mode and Ridership Recovery, Fall 2021
 Source: [7]

Funding and Management

As of 2023, Translink obtains most of its funding from parking tax, motor fuel tax, transit fares, and parts of property taxes within the South Coast British Columbia Transportation Authority Service Region [19]. Canada Community-Building Fund, Public

Transit Infrastructure Fund, and Public Transit Infrastructure Fund form a significant portion of Translink's federal government funding, and the provincial government contributes 40% to the program [20]. With usage of low carbon fuels in their fleets, Translink estimates \$11.5 million is obtained through carbon credits under the BC Renewable and Low Carbon Fuel Requirements Regulation since 2017 [20]. Translink also develops a Green Bond program where funds raised are allocated in bus electrification upgrade and infrastructure expansion, "eco-mode escalator" upgrades, and bike network maintenance [20]. The green bonds were issued in 2018, 2019, and 2022 with a total of 900 million dollars [20].

While motor fuel tax and parking tax offer a great source of income and demand management measures, reduction in internal-combustion-engine-vehicles (ICEVs) and vehicle counts may impact the cash flow from these sources. Hence, Translink should consider seeking alternative funding sources such as real estate development when transitioning into a transit oriented model, as highlighted in the case study section.

As a first step in adapting the real estate development model, the West Broadway and Arbutus Development project is partnered with PCI Development. It will be the first real estate project from Translink's attempt to generate alternative revenue other than fares and government funding [21]. The project will be a thirty storey mixed-use rental building near future Arbutus SkyTrain station and Broadway subway terminal station that aims to provide sustainable housing and public transit options [21].

Therefore, real estate development model can solve long term funding issues when expanding the public transit system while also provide needed housings around stations and transit hubs.

Case Study: Tokyo

By examining other cities' transit systems, Vancouver CMA can gain new insights and policies, along with a fresh perspective on how to improve the current transit system.

Tokyo is a worthy and deserving case study for evaluation. With 13,523 million annual ridership, the Greater Tokyo Area (GTA) has a total of 48 individual private rail operators, 4,715 km of tracks, and more than 2,210 routes serving its citizens [22].

Average track density in Tokyo is 300m/sq.km and 1010m/sq.km in the city core [23].

High track density suggests increased coverage and transit lines for rail based transit systems to be able to serve this large population under efficient means. Tokyo's metro system alone has the highest number of riders across the globe at 3,921 million, followed by Moscow at 2,561 million, and Shanghai at 2,209 million [24].

Unlike cities in North America, Tokyo has adopted transit-oriented development rather than demand-oriented service like that of Vancouver's CMA [22]. The transit oriented development model maximizes efficiency of the public transit system within the desired service area [25]. For instance, a "rail-integrated community" which consists of station hubs, mixed-use buildings and station centre areas are developed by rail companies [22]. These communities are common transit developments in Tokyo because these hubs create a point of interest for transit users and residents, which would increase the

stop's traffic flow while commuters have easy access to such buildings, benefiting both parties [22]. Meanwhile, railway companies can obtain funding from surrounding real estate developments. Greater Tokyo Area's railway operators are privately owned and are for profit companies that rely on real estate projects, ticket fares, and commercial facilities to earn profits [22]. The competitive environment and effective funding model leads to consistent service coverage expansion and better service quality [22]. As a result, Translink can consider adapting the transit oriented development model, become involved in providing commercial facilities, such as station malls, in/near major transport hubs, and increase residential real estate development projects near newly developed stations when expanding the system.

Conclusion

Insufficient FTN coverage, underestimation of catchment areas, utilization of the demand oriented development, low ridership outside of the City of Vancouver, increased population growth and severe congestion are reasons why Translink should expand and update their system using the transit oriented development model. The transit oriented model can offer additional cash flow to help achieve transit expansion and improve service quality, in addition to current demands and tax incomes. However, when engaging in real estate development, early capital investments are required to accelerate the project. Considering this fact, the government can partner with Translink to create both private and social housing around the transit oriented communities. However, if no action is taken, congestion and vehicle emissions would increase, as service quality decreases and population density increases to the maximum transit

system capacity. Consequently, people will seek alternative ways to travel when coverage and frequency is low [26]. Ultimately, environmental issues with transportation are highly dependent on the efficiency and coverage in the public transit system. Indeed, it is only Translink that possesses the capabilities and behemoth support to reduce emissions at a great magnitude.

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